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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

This data review examines the Global Welfare State Information System (WeSIS), an interactive web-based platform developed by the Collaborative Research Centre (CRC) 1342 at the University of Bremen. WeSIS provides comprehensive global data on the development of social policies since 1880, covering over 1,400 indicators across areas such as health, education, family policy, labor, and international linkages. While WeSIS offers valuable resources for comparative welfare state research, the review identifies gaps in data coverage, particularly for post-Soviet states, and notes inconsistencies in historical coding. Continuous updates reflect its status as a “living object”. Funded by the DFG, WeSIS combines original CRC data with international sources, supporting both macro-quantitative analysis and in-depth country studies.

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Data Review – Global Welfare State Information System (WeSIS)

The Global Welfare State Information System “WeSIS” is an “interactive, web-based information system on global dynamics of social policy” (11). Developed by the Collaborative Research Centre (CRC) 1342 at the University of Bremen, WeSIS offers comprehensive data and analytical tools for researchers and policymakers interested in social policy developments worldwide (11).

WeSIS aims “to describe, map, analyze, and explain state policies globally since 1880 for countries with at least 500,000 inhabitants (as of today)” (11). The platform mirrors the analytical approach of the CRC for exploring how social policies are shaped by national attributes and cross-border interdependencies – with a particular focus on the role of international organizations in fostering global policy coordination (11).

Key Features

WeSIS provides data on the “introduction of state social policies, their generosity, and inclusiveness [...] over time”, as well as on “trans- and international (inter-) dependencies [...] [and] national attributes” (11). It provides, among others, an overview of the year major policy programs were introduced and the first year of international organization membership for each country, alongside time series of economic, social, and political data (20). All indicators are described in a separate “collaborative codebook” (20) called WeSISpedia together with common coding rules and standards.

Furthermore, the platform includes various tools for data analysis, such as correlation and map tools, indicator explorer pages, and country profiles (11). Users can – for example – “save a specific selection of indicators, countries, and time points as a user-specific dataset that can be (a) downloaded [...], and (b) be made publicly available keeping a unique identifier” (11).

The system “was built in co-creation with the CRC’s policy scholars” (11), incorporating “user-centered design processes” (11) to ensure the platform meets the needs of social scientists (11). Over a three-year period, the researchers and developers conducted “co-creation workshops, interviews, surveys, and user studies” (León et al. 2022: 1) to iteratively design the platform (León et al. 2022: 1-2). This approach ensured that the system’s functionalities – such as data “harmonization, validation, [and] exploration” (León et al. 2022: 1) – were tailored to the actual workflows of social policy researchers (León et al. 2022: 1). Importantly, the co-design process not only shaped the technical features but also fostered a sense of ownership among participants, leading to successful adoption of the system (León et al. 2022: 1, 7).

The platform allows users to explore the data utilizing several visualizations. Beyond different graphs for single indicators, as of now (August 2025) the system allows the

interactive creation of a choropleth map “visualizing a Metric indicator” (18) as well as a visualization of correlations in which multiple indicator-country combinations can be chosen “to compute a correlation matrix based on Pearson’s product-moment correlation coefficient” (18).

The country profiles provide an in-depth, standardized overview of social policy developments across a wide range of countries, making them very valuable for comparative research.

Indicators

The indicators offered by WeSIS incorporate a wide range of topics that generally cover the areas of social policies, national attributes and global linkages. Each of those topics includes up to eight subtopics (see table 1), which again include multiple indicators (13). In total WeSIS covers over 1,400 indicators – with indicators per year varying between 92 and 1,407 (as of August 2025) (19).

Table 1: Indicators

Topic	Sub-topics
Social Policies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Old age and survivors (Old-age) 2) Labour and labour market (Labour law; Unemployment insurance; Work-injury) 3) Health and long-term care (Healthcare; Long-term care; Tuberculosis) 4) Education and training (Attainment; Curriculum; Legislation; Participation; Resources) 5) Family and gender policies (Child benefits; Childcare & early education; Leave; Total) 6) Immigrant social rights (Direct restriction; Indirect restriction) 7) Social assistance rights 8) Social expenditures (OECD)
National Attributes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Policy legacies (Enslaved labor production) 2) Economic and financial factors (Economics; Finance; Labour market) 3) Political factors (Politics; Polity) 4) Social structure (Economic inequality; Human development; Labour market participation; Population; Social inequality) 5) Culture (Cultural spheres; Religion; Sexuality, relationships, and gender) 6) Geography (Border length; Capital city; Country midpoint) 7) Sustainable development goals (<i>all 17 SDG goals individual</i>)
Global Linkages	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Communication (Culture) 2) Political institutional linkages (Igo membership) 3) Economic relations (Development aid; Investment; Trade) 4) Migration (Migration; Student mobility) 5) Violent conflicts and colonial dependencies (Colonialism; War)

(source: 13)

Some categories and subcategories contain more indicators than others. In general, it should be noted that WeSIS is considered a “living object”, i.e., both the system and the data are kept working on. A major update to Version 2.7 of the database was released in May 2025, introducing changes to the entity list, homepage, and public script layout, along with new policy fields. As mentioned, WeSIS is continuously updated and improved. For a detailed overview of ongoing developments, see the [Development History](#) page (17). Although WeSIS offers a large number of indicators overall, a random sample (see Appendix) within the field of social policies revealed extensive gaps in data coverage for countries relevant to Discuss Data. These countries include Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan. Of the 35 indicators randomly selected for review (see Appendix), data for all countries and years was available in only six cases. For 26 indicators, data was available for some countries and/or years; in two cases, no data was available for any of the countries reviewed; and lastly for one indicator there was (yet) no information at all (13).

Country Profiles

As previously mentioned, WeSIS further provides detailed country profiles. These offer, as of August 2025, comprehensive information on each country, including basic facts, year of introduction for major policy programs, visualizations and data on membership in international organizations and institutions, social policy indicators, trade partnerships, and a graphic illustrating historical relations.

However, with regard to the countries relevant for Discuss Data, certain critical observations must be noted: While WeSIS appeared to operate under the assumption that Russia is equivalent to the Soviet Union (15; see table 2, marked in blue), this coding practice has since been the subject of a more differentiated discussion. As documented in the updated note on [“counterfactual and related unit coding”](#) (February 2025), efforts have been made to revise and refine such classifications.

Nonetheless, as the implementation of this revised coding is still incomplete, several datasets continue to include pre-1991 data under overarching categories such as Russia, the Soviet Union or the Tsarist Empire. This may significantly affect the interpretation of historical data. As a result, extended time series prior to the dissolution of the Soviet Union are still missing or ambiguously coded for several relevant countries, including Russia itself. Comparative analyses are therefore yet – as of August 2025 – limited.

This classification also leads to incorrectness in some instances of institutional membership data. If countries joined international organizations prior to 1991 but did so as integral republics or entities, WeSIS may incorrectly list their accession data as (post-) 1991 (see table 2, institutions marked in red). For example, Ukraine, then the Ukrainian Soviet Socialist Republic, was a founding member of the United Nations in

1945. Nevertheless, the Ukrainian country profile wrongly records 1991 as the year of accession (6; 16).

Notably, the country profiles also feature a visualization indicating the timing of major social policy implementations in each country relative to the global median (12). This graphic provides a potentially valuable way of comparison.

Table 2: Relevant Country Coverage for Discuss Data (12)

Country	Coverage
Armenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1918, Independence 1918-1922, Soviet Union 1922-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing Accession to International Organizations: ILO, IMF, UN, UNESCO, World Bank, WHO 1992; WTO 2003 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Azerbaijan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1918, Independence 1918-1920, Soviet Union 1920-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing Accession to International Organizations: ILO, IMF, UN, UNESCO, World Bank, WHO 1992 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Belarus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1917, Soviet Union 1918-1941, Germany 1941-1943, Soviet Union 1943-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing Accession to International Organizations: ILO, UN, UNESCO, WHO 1991; IMF, World Bank 1992 <i>(wrong accession dates → ILO: correct is 1954 (3); UN: original member in 1945 under country name of “Byelorussian Soviet Socialist Republic” (9); UNESCO: correct is 1954 (10); WHO: correct is 1948 (21))</i>
Estonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1918, Independence 1918-1940, Soviet Union 1940-1941, Germany 1941-1943, Soviet Union 1941-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing Accession to International Organizations: ILO, League of Nations 1921; UN, UNESCO, WHO 1991; IMF, World Bank 1992; WTO 1999; OECD 2010 <i>(wrong accession date → WHO: correct is 1993 (21))</i>
Georgia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1918, Independence 1918-1921, Soviet Union 1921-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing Accession to International Organizations: IMF, UN, UNESCO, World Bank, WHO 1992; ILO 1993; WTO 2000 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Kazakhstan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical Relations: Russia 1848-1922, Soviet Union 1922-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing Accession to International Organizations: IMF, UN, UNESCO, World Bank, WHO 1992; ILO 1993 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Kyrgyzstan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical Relations: Russia 1873-1922, Soviet Union 1922-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accession to International Organizations: ILO, IMF, UN, UNESCO, World Bank, WHO 1992; WTO 1998 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Latvia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1918, Independence 1918-1940, Soviet Union 1940-1941, Germany 1941-1943, Soviet Union 1943-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing • Accession to International Organizations: ILO, League of Nations 1921; UN, UNESCO, WHO 1991; IMF, World Bank 1992; WTO 1999 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Lithuania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1918, Independence 1918-1940, Soviet Union 1940-1941, Germany 1941-1943, Soviet Union 1943-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing • Accession to International Organizations: ILO, League of Nations 1921; UN, UNESCO, WHO 1991; IMF, World Bank 1992; WTO 2001 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Moldova	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1917, Romania 1918-1940, Soviet Union 1940-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing • Accession to International Organizations: ILO, IMF, UN, UNESCO, World Bank, WHO 1992; WTO 2001 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Russia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Relations: Independence 1816 ongoing; Germany 1915-1918, Soviet Union 1922-1941, Germany 1941-1943, Soviet Union 1943-1991 • Accession to International Organizations: ILO, League of Nations 1943; UN 1945; WHO 1948; UNESCO 1950; IMF, World Bank 1992; WTO 2012 <i>(wrong accession dates → ILO: correct is 1934 to 1940 and since 1954 (3); League of Nations: correct is USSR was member between 1934 and 1939 (21); UNESCO: correct is 1954 (10))</i>
Tajikistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Relations: Russia 1895-1922, Soviet Union 1922-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing • Accession to International Organizations: UN, WHO 1992; ILO, IMF, UNESCO, World Bank 1993; WTO 2013 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Turkmenistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Relations: Russia 1881-1922, Soviet Union 1922-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing • Accession to International Organizations: IMF, UN, World Bank, WHO 1992; ILO, UNESCO 1993 (<i>all dates correct</i>)
Ukraine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Relations: Russia 1816-1918, Soviet Union 1919-1941, Germany 1941-1943, Soviet Union 1943-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing • Accession to International Organizations: ILO, UN, UNESCO, WHO 1991; IMF, World Bank 1992; WTO 2008 <i>(wrong accession dates → ILO: correct is 1954 (3); UN: correct is 1945 (9); UNESCO: correct is 1954 (10); WHO: correct is 1948 (21))</i>

Uzbekistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Relations: Russia 1873-1922, Soviet Union 1922-1991, Independence 1991 ongoing • Accession to International Organizations: UN 1991; ILO, IMF, World Bank, WHO 1992; UNESCO 1993 <i>(wrong accession date → UN correct is 1992 (9))</i>
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([ILO](#): International Labour Organization; [IMF](#): International Monetary Fund; [UN](#): United Nations; [UNESCO](#): United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization; [WHO](#): World Health Organization; [WTO](#): World Trade Organization; [OECD](#): Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development; [League of Nations](#); [World Bank](#))

Framework and Data Collection

As mentioned before, the CRC 1342 “describes the development dynamics of social policy as the interaction of national determinants and international or transnational interdependencies” (2). The development of WeSIS started with the first funding phase of the CRC 1342, when the platform was created to support global and historical analysis of welfare state dynamics (2; 11). Within the CRC, six subprojects from Research Area A conduct comprehensive studies on “the socio-political development dynamics of both coverage and generosity for specific social policy fields” (2). These subprojects gather global data across eight policy areas and “feed them into the WeSIS database” (2). To contextualize the macro-quantitative findings, they are “supplemented by in-depth country studies” (2). “Project Area B consists of eight projects which examine the socio-political inclusion and benefit dynamics in case studies and small-N comparisons for selected countries or regions” (2).

WeSIS incorporates original data on social policy dynamics from the CRC 1342 and adds relevant data from various international data providers like the World Bank, World Health Organization (WHO), UNESCO, Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), International Monetary Fund (IMF), or the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) (13). This includes both standardized international datasets and specific data collection projects conducted within the CRC (13). The sources and data providers are documented in the meta data of each individual indicator.

Access and Funding

Access to the data and the platform is free of charge but requires registration with a first and last name, an email address, and a password (as of August 2025).

WeSIS is funded by the DFG, the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. The DFG is mostly funded through the German “federal government (69.7%) and the federal states (29.4%), but also through EU funds and private donations” (1).

Conflict of Interest

This review was produced by members of CRC 1342; while every effort was made to ensure objectivity and academic rigor, potential conflict of interest due to institutional affiliation should be acknowledged.

Note

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Appendix

Sample of Indicator Availability for Countries Relevant to Discuss Data as of July 2025

Country Indicator Topic	Example indicators	Countries and Timeframe	Source
Old age survivors	Introduction		
	Year of introduction of old-age pension program (old_pension_firstlaw)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	Original CRC Data
	Design		
	Design of old-age pension program (old_pension_firstlaw_design)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	Original CRC Data
	Financing		
	Financing of old-age pension program, employee (old_pension_fin_employee)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	Original CRC Data
	Coverage		
Coverage of old-age pension, aggregate (old_pension_cov_tot)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	Original CRC Data	
Restrictions of old-age pension coverage, wage (old_pension_rest_wage)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan,	Original CRC Data	

		Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	
Eligibility criteria			
	Maximal retirement age, female (old_pension_agemax_f)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	Original CRC Data
	Maximal retirement age, male (old_pension_agemax_m)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	Original CRC Data
Benefits			
	Maximal benefit of old-age pension program (old_pension_reprate_max)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	Original CRC Data
	Minimal benefit of old-age pension program (old_pension_reprate_min)	no data available for: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan Latvia: complete data (1922) Russia: complete data (1922)	Original CRC Data
Labour and labour market	Labour law		
	Closed shops (labor_closedshop)	complete data available for 1990 to 2022: Latvia, Lithuania complete data available for 1991 to 2022:	“variable is taken from the CBR Labour Regulation Index Dataset (‘CBR-LRI’),

	<p>Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Ukraine</p> <p>complete data available for 1992 to 2022: Russia</p> <p>no data available: Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan</p>	<p>which provides data on labor laws in 117 countries for the period from (in most cases) 1970 to 2022, except for post-socialist countries (see Adams et al. 2017, 2023)” (14)</p>
Compulsory conciliation or arbitration (labor_comp_conc)	<p>complete data available for 1990 to 2022: Lithuania, Latvia</p> <p>complete data available for 1991 to 2022: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Ukraine</p> <p>complete data available for 1992 to 2022: Russia</p> <p>no data available: Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan</p>	<p>CBR-LRI; Adams et al. 2017, 2023</p>
Employment legislation		
Introduction dates employment legislation (labor_employleg_employpro_regcontract)	<p>Armenia: complete data (1882) Azerbaijan: complete data (1882) Belarus: complete data (1882) Estonia: complete data (1882) Georgia: complete data (1882) Kazakhstan: complete data (1922) Kyrgyzstan: complete data (1922) Latvia: complete data (1882) Lithuania: complete data (1882) Russia: complete data (1882) Tajikistan: complete data (1922) Turkmenistan: complete data (1922) Ukraine: complete data (1882) Uzbekistan: complete data (1922)</p> <p>Moldova: no data available</p>	<p>Original CRC Data</p>
Equalizing		
Agency workers have the right to equal treatment (labor_awork_et)	<p>complete data available for 1970 to 2022: Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Latvia</p> <p>complete data available for 1991 to 2022:</p>	<p>CRC Compiled Data (CBR-LRI)</p>

	<p>Lithuania, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Georgia, Estonia, Belarus, Azerbaijan, Armenia</p> <p>complete data available for 1991 to 2022: Ukraine, Moldova</p> <p>complete data available for 1992 to 2022: Russia</p>	
Labour law		
<p>Equalising function (labor_equa_func)</p>	<p>complete data available for 1990 to 2022: Latvia, Lithuania</p> <p>complete data available for 1991 to 2013: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Ukraine</p> <p>complete data available for 1992 to 2013: Russia</p> <p>no available data: Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan</p>	CRC Compiled Data (CBR-LRI)
Privileging		
<p>Minimum qualifying period of service for normal case of unjust dismissal (labor_min_qua_per)</p>	<p>complete data available for 1970 to 2022: Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan</p> <p>complete data available for 1990 to 2022: Latvia, Lithuania</p> <p>complete data available for 1991 to 2022: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Ukraine</p> <p>complete data available for 1992 to 2022: Russia</p>	CRC Compiled Data (CBR-LRI)
Standard-setting		
<p>Law imposes procedural constraints on dismissal</p>	<p>complete data available for 1970 to 2022: Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan</p>	CRC Compiled Data (CBR-LRI)

(labor_pro_dis_con)	<p>complete data available for 1990 to 2022: Latvia, Lithuania</p> <p>complete data available for 1991 to 2022: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Ukraine</p> <p>complete data available for 1992 to 2022: Russia</p>	
Unemployment		
Unemployment. First law beneficiaries. (labor_unemp_firstlaw_beneficiaries)	<p>Armenia: complete data (1991) Azerbaijan: complete data (2001) Belarus: complete data (2006) Estonia: complete data (1991) Georgia: complete data (1991) Kazakhstan: complete data (2003) Kyrgyzstan: complete data (2003) Latvia: complete data (1991) Lithuania: complete data (1990) Moldova: complete data (1992) Russia: complete data (1917) Tajikistan: complete data (2003) Turkmenistan: complete data (1991)</p> <p>Ukraine: no available data Uzbekistan: no available data</p>	Original CRC Data
Unemployment insurance		
Unemployment Insurance Law. Benefit Progressivity (abor_unemp_benefit_progressivity)	<p>complete data available for 1900 to 2019: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan</p>	Original CRC Data
Work-injury		
Work-injury. Agricultural workers first law introduction year. (labor_workinjury_firstlaw_agriworkers)	<p>no data available: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan</p> <p>Estonia: complete data (1936) Latvia: complete data (1927) Lithuania: complete data (1939)</p>	Original CRC Data
Healthcare		

Health and long-term care	Capital health expenditures as percentage of GDP (health_hc_financing_caphealthexp_pergdp_wb)	complete data available for 2000 to 2012: Latvia complete data available for 2000 to 2015: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan, Lithuania complete data available for 2001 to 2015: Georgia complete data available for 2003 to 2015: Kazakhstan some data available: Turkmenistan: 2004 and 2010 Estonia: 2000-2007 and 2012-2015	World Bank
	Long-term care		
	Domestic general government expenditure on long-term care (health) in million NCU (health_LTC_financing_GovExp_LTHealth_MiNCU_WHO)	Kazakhstan: complete data (2016) Kyrgyzstan: complete data (2016) Russia: complete data (2016) Tajikistan: complete data (2016) no data available: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan	World Health Organization (WHO)
	Tuberculosis		
Estimated percentage of new TB cases with rifampicin resistant TB (e_rr_pct_new)	complete data available for 2015 to 2021: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan	WHO	
Education and training	Attainment		
	Educational attainment: at least bachelor's or equivalent (ISCED 6 or higher), population 25+ years, both sexes (edu_isced6_	some data available: Armenia: 2001, 2011, 2015, 2017 Azerbaijan: 1999, 2007, 2008, 2013-2017 Georgia: 2012, 2014, 2016, 2017 Kazakhstan: 2009, 2018 Latvia: 2013-2016, 2018 Lithuania: 2013-2017 Moldova: 2013-2015, 2018	UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS)

attainment_25+_uis)	Russia: 2010 Tajikistan: 2017 Uzbekistan: 2013-2016, 2018 no data available: Belarus, Estonia, Turkmenistan, Ukraine	
Curriculum		
Religious education compulsory (edu_relig)	Belarus: complete data available for 1919-2019 Estonia: complete data available for 2002-2019 Moldova: complete data available for 2014-2019 Russia: complete data available 1880-2019 Tajikistan: complete data available for 2010-2019 Ukraine: complete data available for 1996-2019 Uzbekistan: complete data available for 1992-2019 no data available: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Turkmenistan	Original CRC Data
Legislation		
Age of first selection (edu_first_select)	complete data available for 2002 to 2019: Belarus, Estonia, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Tajikistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan no data available: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Russia, Turkmenistan	Original CRC Data
Participation		
Enrollment trend in primary education (edu_pri_enroll)	complete data available for 1880 to 2018: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan no data available: Turkmenistan	Original CRC Data
Resources		
Initial household funding of education as a	some data available: Azerbaijan: 2008-2014, 2016, 2017 Belarus: 2014-2017	UIS

	percentage of GDP (edu_exp_all_prv_ihh_uis)	Estonia: 2007-2011, 2014, 2015 Georgia: 2016, 2017 Kazakhstan: 2002, 2005-2007, 2015-2018 Kyrgyzstan: 2015-2017 Latvia: 1999-2016 Lithuania: 2005-2016 Russia: 2012, 2015, 2016 Tajikistan: 2001-2009 Ukraine: 1998, 2000, 2011-2014, 2016, 2017 no data available: Armenia, Moldova, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan	
Family and gender policies	Child benefits		
	Existence of both employment-based and citizen- or residency-based child benefits (fam_cben_avail_both)	complete data available for 1880 to 2021: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan	Original CRC Data
	Childcare & early education		
	Year workplace childcare legislation was passed (fam_fcare_law_year)	Armenia: complete data (1936) Azerbaijan: complete data (1936) Belarus: complete data (1936, 1992, 1999) Estonia: complete data (1928, 1944, 1971) Georgia: complete data (1936) Kazakhstan: complete data (1936m 1972) Kyrgyzstan: complete data (1936) Latvia: complete data (1944, 1971) Lithuania: complete data (1944, 1971) Russia: complete data (1932, 1936) Tajikistan: complete data (1936) Turkmenistan: complete data (1936) Ukraine: complete data (1936, 1972) Uzbekistan: complete data (1936) no data available: Moldova	?
Leave			
Parental leave replacement rate (fam_par_leave_amount_repl_WBL)	data available for the years 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016, 2018: Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Moldova, Kazakhstan, Latvia,	World Bank	

		Lithuania, Russia, Tajikistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan no data available: Armenia, Georgia, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan	
	Total		
	Total public social expenditure on families (% of GDP)	no information	?
Immigrant social rights	Direct restriction		
	Access to social assistance for permanent residents (isr_permmig_soc_ass_access_s)	no data available: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan	Original CRC Data
	Indirect restriction		
	Consequence for dependence on social assistance for permanent residents (isr_permmig_soc_ass_conseq_s)	no data available: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan	Original CRC Data
Social assistance rights	National arrangement		
	Inclusiveness of Social Assistance Entitlements of Adults with Disabilities (FLOOR) (sar_sys_d_inc_floor)	data for 2013: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan no data available: Belarus, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Ukraine	?
Social expenditures	Oecd		
	Public social expenditure social assistance policies (in kind) as percent of GDP (socx_oecd_public_social_kind)	complete data available for 1997 to 2021: Latvia no data available: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan	?

(source: 5)